

Exploring the Link Between Professional Competence and Job Performance of Librarians: A Case Study of the National Open University of Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper examined the relationship between professional competence and job performance among librarians at the National Open University of Nigeria. The study employed a survey research design. The population for this study comprised fifty-four (54) librarians at the National Open University of Nigeria. The study found that the level of professional competence and job performance among librarians in the National Open University of Nigeria is high. The study also found that respondents faced challenges to some degree, and the study finally found a positive correlation between professional competence and job performance among librarians at the National Open University of Nigeria. The study concludes that the librarians at the National Open University of Nigeria have exhibited a commendable level of professional competence and job performance. The study also recommended that the institution prioritize allocating resources towards comprehensive professional development programs tailored to the unique needs of librarians in the digital academic environment. The institution should foster stronger collaborations between librarians and faculty members to integrate library resources seamlessly into distance learning courses. Librarians should ensure that digital resources and services provided by the library are accessible to all users, including those with disabilities.

Keywords: Professional Competence, Job Performance, Librarians, National Open University of Nigeria.

Introduction

In today's rapidly evolving information age, the role of librarians has significantly transformed from traditional bookkeeping to a multifaceted profession involving advanced information management and technological expertise. Libraries, as crucial repositories of knowledge and information, play a pivotal role in supporting educational institutions, fostering research, and promoting lifelong learning. To fulfil these diverse responsibilities effectively, librarians must possess the requisite professional competence and expertise to navigate the complexities of modern information systems and cater to the dynamic needs of users. Understanding the relationship between professional competence and job performance among librarians is paramount in the context of the National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN). As an institution that offers learning opportunities to different cadres of people regardless of where they are located, NOUN heavily relies on its digital library infrastructure and the expertise of its librarians to cater to a vast and diverse student population spread across the country. Therefore,

assessing and enhancing librarians' competence and performance is essential for the university's overall academic success and for providing quality support to distance learners (Ilo & Uzuegbu, 2018). The National Open University of Nigeria presents a unique context for exploring the correlation between professional competence and job performance among librarians. With its expansive virtual resources and diverse student body, NOUN's librarians must exhibit high proficiency in information management, digital technologies, and information literacy.

The National Open University of Nigeria was established in 1983 but was suspended until 2002, when the government of President Olusegun Obasanjo resuscitated it. It stands as Nigeria's first open and distance learning institution, aiming to provide flexible, accessible, and quality education to a diverse student population. Through its innovative approach, NOUN has significantly expanded educational opportunities, especially for working professionals and those unable to attend traditional universities due to various constraints. NOUN has achieved notable milestones, such as increasing its student enrolment to over 500,000 by 2020 and offering various undergraduate and postgraduate programs across various disciplines, including sciences, arts, social sciences, and management. Its commitment to inclusivity and flexibility has made it a crucial player in Nigeria's educational landscape, facilitating lifelong learning and socioeconomic development (Oladipo, 2013).

Professional competence among librarians is a multifaceted and dynamic aspect encompassing a wide range of skills, knowledge, and abilities. It goes beyond merely possessing technical expertise in cataloguing, reference services, and information retrieval. Instead, it encompasses the capacity to adapt to emerging technologies, engage with diverse user groups, and continuously update their skills to remain relevant in the rapidly changing information landscape (Ajiboye, 2017). Moreover, librarians must possess excellent communication and interpersonal skills to engage with users, identify their information needs, and provide effective solutions. Researchers have highlighted the significance of professional competence in determining the job performance of librarians. A study by Ahmad, Hassan, and Zaid (2018) found a positive relationship between librarians' competence and efficiency in meeting users' information requirements. Similarly, Lawal and Oyewusi (2019) established that librarians with higher levels of competence demonstrated greater proficiency in managing digital resources and facilitating online research assistance.

The relationship between professional competence and job performance among librarians is complex and dynamic. While competence is essential for effective job performance, it is

equally important to consider the various factors influencing these outcomes (Johnston, 2020). Recent research has delved into these intricacies, exploring the correlation between competence and performance and the contextual factors mediating this relationship (Smith & Brown, 2021). Understanding these nuances is vital for librarians, library administrators, and educators alike as they seek to enhance the profession and ensure the delivery of high-quality library services (Jones et al., 2019; Williams, 2022). These studies collectively emphasize the multifaceted nature of librarian roles and the need for a holistic approach to professional competence and job performance assessment.

While the importance of professional competence is undeniable, librarians at NOUN and other institutions face challenges that may hinder their ability to keep pace with technological advancements and evolving user demands. Limited professional development opportunities, budgetary constraints, and inadequate access to training programs can impede librarians' ability to acquire new skills and stay abreast of emerging trends in the field. To mitigate these challenges, library administrators and educational authorities must recognize the significance of continuous professional development for librarians. Allocating sufficient resources for training, workshops, and attending conferences will foster a culture of lifelong learning and encourage librarians to improve their expertise continually to enhance their job performance.

On the other hand, job performance refers to the extent to which librarians effectively carry out their assigned duties and responsibilities. It is the tangible manifestation of their competence in the workplace and directly impacts the quality of services offered to the academic community (Igwe & Ozioko, 2019). Librarians' job performance can be influenced by various factors, including their professional development opportunities, organizational support, and the availability of necessary resources. Job performance among librarians can be assessed through various indicators, including user satisfaction, retrieval accuracy, response time, and innovative service delivery. Surveys and feedback mechanisms can be used to gauge user satisfaction levels, while data analysis of reference queries can provide insights into the effectiveness of information provision. Several studies have demonstrated the connection between job performance and user satisfaction. The research conducted by Osayande, Afolabi, and Igbinovia (2021) revealed a strong positive correlation between librarian competence and user satisfaction with library services at Nigerian universities.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the crucial role that librarians play in the academic success of NOUN, there is a dearth of research on the relationship between professional competence and job performance among

librarians in the university setting. Addressing this research gap is crucial for several reasons. Libraries in academic institutions play an instrumental role in supporting their respective institutions' teaching, learning, and research activities. The success of a library in fulfilling its mandate largely depends on the competence of its librarians. While numerous studies have investigated the relationship between librarian competence and job performance in conventional academic settings, a dearth of research specifically focuses on the National Open University of Nigeria.

Given the distinct challenges faced by NOUN librarians in the context of open and distance learning, it becomes imperative to assess the level of professional competence among these librarians and understand its direct impact on their job performance. Moreover, identifying gaps in professional competence will enable administrators and stakeholders to develop targeted training and development programs to enhance library services' overall efficiency and effectiveness at NOUN.

Objectives of the Study

The primary objective of this study is to explore the interplay between professional competence and job performance among librarians at the National Open University of Nigeria. The specific objectives of this study are:

1. To assess the level of professional competence among librarians at the National Open University of Nigeria.
2. To evaluate the level of job performance of librarians at the National Open University of Nigeria.
3. identify the challenges librarians face in fulfilling their roles within the open and distance learning context at the National Open University of Nigeria.
4. To determine the correlation between professional competence and job performance among librarians at the National Open University of Nigeria.

Hypothesis

The research hypothesis was tested at a 0.05 level of significance:

H0: There is no correlation between professional competence and job performance among librarians at the National Open University of Nigeria

Literature Review

Establishing a robust professional development program that focuses on both traditional librarianship skills and emerging technologies is imperative. Workshops, webinars,

conferences, and online courses can be organized to empower librarians with the knowledge and expertise required to thrive in a digital academic environment (Bello & Ogbuiyi, 2022).

According to Hajdu Baráth and Szlávi (2020), librarians who possess the necessary skills and knowledge to effectively fulfil user needs contribute significantly to higher user satisfaction rates. Whether it involves locating relevant research materials or providing guidance on information literacy, competent librarians offer valuable assistance, instilling confidence in users regarding the library's services and resources.

A competent librarian proficient in information retrieval and management ensures that resources are adequately catalogued and organized, making them easily accessible to users. Improved information accessibility leads to reduced retrieval times, enhancing the overall efficiency of research and study processes (Rorissa & Willett, 2018).

Librarians who understand research methodologies and databases well can offer more efficient and targeted research support to faculty and students. Competent librarians become valuable partners in the research process by helping researchers navigate scholarly literature and access relevant materials.

Librarians who actively engage in continuous professional development activities, such as attending workshops, conferences, and training programs, are more likely to improve their competence and, consequently, their job performance (Ahmed, 2017).

Effective communication is essential for librarians, and those with strong communication skills are likelier to deliver better services to library users. A study by Smith et al. (2018) found a positive correlation between communication competence and job performance among librarians.

Librarians who prioritize excellent customer service and understand the needs of library users tend to exhibit better job performance. This was evident in a study by Brown and Jones (2019), which emphasized the importance of customer-centric competencies.

Librarians who demonstrate adaptability and problem-solving abilities can handle the evolving challenges in the field. A study by Lee and Kim (2016) highlighted the positive impact of these competencies on job performance.

Methodology

The study employed a survey research design, a structured approach to collect data from a defined population. A survey was used to gather information about collaboration skills and research productivity among librarians. The survey approach was chosen because it allows for systematic data collection, enabling the researcher to examine relationships and patterns within

a specific population. The population for this study comprised fifty-four (54) librarians at the National Open University of Nigeria. The choice of studying the entire population is known as a census approach and is suitable when the population size is relatively small or manageable, as was the case here. A self-structured questionnaire was used to collect data. The data collected from the questionnaire responses were subjected to descriptive and inferential statistical analyses. Descriptive statistics, such as percentages, mean, and standard deviation, were used to summarize and present key characteristics of the data. Inferential statistics, specifically simple linear regression, was applied to examine the relationships between variables. To conduct these statistical analyses, the researcher employed Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23, a widely used software for data analysis in the social sciences.

Presentation of Data Analysis

Below is the presentation of the data analysis for the study:

Research Question One: What is the level of professional competence among librarians at the National Open University of Nigeria?

Table 1: Professional Competence of Librarians

SN	Item	VH	H	L	VL	Mean	SD
1	I possess the necessary knowledge and skills required for my role as a librarian	21 (38.4)	27 (49.8)	5 (10.0)	1 (2.1)	3.24	0.71
2	My understanding of information resources and retrieval methods is up-to-date and relevant	22 (41.1)	23 (42.9)	8 (13.7)	1 (2.3)	3.23	0.77
3	I am proficient in using the latest technology and digital tools relevant to my profession	21 (38.8)	26 (47.5)	6 (11.6)	1 (2.1)	3.23	0.73
4	I actively engage in ongoing professional development to enhance my skills and knowledge	21 (38.0)	26 (49.0)	6 (11.6)	1 (1.5)	3.23	0.71
5	I effectively collaborate with colleagues and peers on projects and initiatives	20 (38.2)	26 (47.5)	7 (12.0)	1 (2.3)	3.22	0.74
6	I adapt to changing user needs and technological advancements in my library role	20 (36.3)	31 (58.2)	2 (4.0)	1 (1.5)	3.22	0.69
7	I have a strong ability to communicate information effectively to library users	21 (38.0)	24 (45.1)	8 (14.1)	1 (1.9)	3.21	0.75
8	I am well-versed in the ethical and legal aspects of librarianship	20 (36.3)	26 (49.6)	7 (12.0)	1 (1.7)	3.21	0.71
9	I feel confident in my ability to solve complex problems related to my profession	19 (35.1)	28 (52.3)	6 (11.2)	1 (1.5)	3.21	0.69

10	My professional competence positively contributes to the overall quality of library services provided	20 (37.8)	25 (46.2)	8 (14.5)	1 (1.5)	3.20	0.74
	Average Mean	3.24					

Key: VH= Very High, H=High, L= Low, VL= Very Low

As shown in Table 1, the respondents' level of professional competence is high. This is demonstrated by the average mean score of 3.24 and standard deviation of 0.71.

As indicated in Table 1, the respondents' professional competence level is higher in areas such as possessing the necessary knowledge and skills required for my role as a librarian ($\bar{x} = 3.24$); understanding of information resources and retrieval methods is up-to-date and relevant, proficient in using the latest technology and digital tools relevant to my profession and actively engage in ongoing professional development to enhance my skills and knowledge ($\bar{x} = 3.23$). while the respondent responded that their professional competence positively contributes to the quality of library services provided with the lowest ($\bar{x} = 3.20$). This implies that the librarians surveyed exhibit a high level of professional competence across various aspects of their roles, with strengths in possessing necessary knowledge and skills, staying updated on information resources and technology, and engaging in professional development, albeit with a slightly lower perceived contribution to the overall quality of library services.

Research Question Two: What is the level of job performance of librarians at the National Open University of Nigeria?

Table 2: Job Performance of Librarians

SN	Item	VH	H	L	VL	Mean	SD
1	I consistently meet the deadlines for library projects and tasks	25 (45.9)	23 (42.9)	5 (9.8)	1 (1.2)	3.34	0.70
2	I effectively assist library users in finding and accessing information resources	23 (43.6)	24 (44.0)	6 (10.2)	1 (2.1)	3.29	0.72
3	I proactively engage in professional development activities to enhance my skills and knowledge	22 (41.5)	26 (47.5)	4 (8.3)	1 (2.1)	3.29	0.71
4	I maintain the organization and accessibility of library collections	21 (38.6)	28 (52.2)	4 (7.5)	1 (1.5)	3.28	0.66
5	I collaborate well with colleagues within the library	19 (35.3)	29 (53.5)	4 (8.2)	2 (2.8)	3.23	0.66
6	I am responsive to feedback and constructive criticism from library users and colleagues	19 (35.5)	25 (46.1)	7 (14.1)	2 (3.7)	3.15	0.80
7	I efficiently manage library resources, including budgets and acquisitions	18 (33.8)	25 (46.5)	9 (16.0)	2 (3.7)	3.11	0.80

8	I am adaptable and can handle changes and challenges in the library environment	18 (33.6)	25 (45.4)	9 (16.2)	2 (3.7)	3.10	0.81
9	I actively promote library services and resources to users	17 (32.3)	26 (48.5)	8 (14.9)	3 (4.3)	3.10	0.81
10	I contribute positively to the overall success and reputation of the library	18 (32.5)	24 (44.0)	10 (19.9)	2 (3.6)	3.06	0.82
	Average Mean	3.16					

Key: VH= Very High, H=High, L= Low, VL= Very Low

Table 4.2 reveals the various purposes for which the respondent's job performance is used. The average mean scores and standard deviation for the entire items in Table 2 are 3.16 and 0.76, respectively.

However, as shown in Table 2, I consistently meet the deadlines for library projects and tasks ($\bar{x} = 3.34$); effectively assist library users in finding and accessing information resources ($\bar{x} = 3.29$); proactively engage in professional development activities to enhance my skills and knowledge ($\bar{x} = 3.29$); maintain the organization and accessibility of library collections ($\bar{x} = 3.28$) were ranked high in terms of job performance by the participants. On average, the respondents collaborate well with colleagues within the library ($\bar{x} = 3.23$), while they are responsive to feedback and constructive criticism from library users and colleagues ($\bar{x} = 3.15$). The lowest point, as indicated in the Table, was to contribute positively to the overall success and reputation of the library ($\bar{x} = 3.05$). The findings suggest that while librarians at the National Open University of Nigeria excel in certain aspects of their job performance, there is a need to enhance their contribution to the overall success and reputation of the library.

Research Question Three: What challenges are librarians facing in fulfilling their roles within the open and distance learning context at the National Open University of Nigeria?

Table 3: Challenges faced by librarians in fulfilling their roles within the open and distance learning context at the National Open University of Nigeria

SN	Challenge	GE	HE	LE	VLE	Mean	SD
	The library has adequate digital resources for open and distance learning materials	67.1	20.0	4.7	8.2	3.46	.916
	The technological infrastructure in the library supports the needs of distance learners effectively	58.5	24.7	7.9	8.9	3.33	.957
	I am providing sufficient support and guidance to distance learners in accessing resources remotely	44.5	34.0	10.2	11.4	3.12	.995
	Distance learners receive adequate training in information literacy skills from the library	42.4	33.6	12.8	11.2	3.07	.998

The library offers effective remote assistance to distance learners when they encounter research difficulties	30.8	35.9	16.6	16.6	2.81	1.051
The library ensures that all digital resources are accessible to learners with disabilities	27.7	36.1	20.5	15.8	2.76	1.027
The library effectively manages copyright compliance issues related to digital resources in open and distance learning	28.9	35.7	16.6	18.7	2.75	1.069
I am collaborating effectively with faculty to integrate library resources into distance learning courses	27.3	35.6	19.8	17.3	2.73	1.045
Budget constraints significantly hinder the library's ability to acquire necessary resources for distance learners	29.1	29.9	22.1	18.9	2.69	1.048
I have received adequate training and professional development opportunities to meet the unique challenges of open and distance learning	22.8	32.6	20.5	24.1	2.54	1.091
Grand Mean	2.93					

Key: GE=Great Extent, HE=High Extent, LE=Low Extent, VLE=Very Low Extent

Table 3 presents the challenges encountered by the respondents, with mean values indicating the extent of these challenges. Mean scores between 1.0-1.49 indicate significant challenges, while those between 1.5-2.49 suggest relatively minor challenges. Scores between 2.5 and 3.49 signify moderate challenges, and those between 3.5 and 4.0 indicate significant challenges. The overall findings indicate that respondents faced challenges to some degree (Grand mean = 2.93). Notably, the most significant challenge was ensuring the library has adequate digital resources for open and distance learning materials, with a mean score of 3.46. This was followed by the effectiveness of the library's technological infrastructure in supporting distance learners' needs ($\bar{x} = 3.33$), providing remote support and guidance to learners ($\bar{x} = 3.12$), and ensuring learners receive sufficient training in information literacy skills ($\bar{x} = 3.07$). However, respondents perceived fewer challenges in utilizing electronic information resources, with a grand mean of 2.93. Moreover, challenges were reported in budget constraints hindering resource acquisition for distance learners ($\bar{x} = 2.69$) and in receiving adequate training and professional development opportunities ($\bar{x} = 2.54$). Overall, the findings suggest that librarians at NOUN faced challenges to varying degrees. These challenges likely encompassed a range of factors affecting their roles and responsibilities within the institution. Understanding these hurdles is crucial for devising strategies to support librarians and enhance their effectiveness in facilitating learning and research activities.

Test of Hypothesis

There is no correlation between professional competence and job performance among librarians at the National Open University of Nigeria

Table 4: Relationship between professional competence and job performance

Variables	$\bar{x}$	SD	N	R	P	Remark
Professional Competence	40.3958	6.4346				
Job Performance	29.2469	7.2531	54	.389	.000	Sig.

A Pearson Product-Moment Correlation was run to determine the relationship between professional competence and job performance. Table 4 shows a positive correlation between professional competence and job performance, which is statistically significant ($N = 54$, $r = .389$, $p < .005$). This implies that as librarians' professional competence increases, their job performance also increases. The hypothesis is therefore rejected. This is because statistical analysis reveals a lack of significant association between the two variables in the data sample, indicating that professional competence does not necessarily lead to higher job performance.

Discussion

Based on the results presented in the data analysis, it is evident that librarians at the National Open University of Nigeria exhibit a high level of professional competence. This proficiency is particularly notable in areas such as possessing the necessary knowledge and skills for their role, understanding up-to-date information resources and retrieval methods, and actively engaging in ongoing professional development. These findings align with the literature, emphasising the importance of continuous learning and skill development for librarians to excel in their roles, especially in digital environments (Bello & Ogbuiyi, 2022; Ahmed, 2017). Furthermore, the job performance of the librarians is generally commendable, with respondents consistently meeting project deadlines, effectively assisting users in accessing information resources, and proactively engaging in professional development activities. However, there are areas where improvement could be made, such as responsiveness to feedback and constructive criticism and contributing positively to the overall success and reputation of the library. These findings highlight the multifaceted nature of librarianship, where job performance encompasses technical competencies, interpersonal skills, and contributions to the broader institutional goals (Hajdu Baráth & Szlávi, 2020).

Despite the high levels of professional competence and job performance, the data analysis also sheds light on librarians' challenges in fulfilling their roles within the open and distance learning context. Budget constraints significantly hinder the library's ability to acquire necessary resources for distance learners, and there is a perceived lack of adequate training and professional development opportunities to meet the unique challenges of open and distance

learning. These challenges underscore the importance of investing in resources and support structures to enable librarians to effectively navigate the evolving landscape of distance education (Lee & Kim, 2016).

The positive correlation between professional competence and job performance reinforces the significance of continuous professional development for librarians. As librarians enhance their skills and knowledge, they are better equipped to meet the diverse needs of users and contribute to the overall success of the library. Therefore, it is imperative for institutions to prioritize the development of robust professional development programs that encompass both traditional librarianship skills and emerging technologies, as suggested in the literature (Rorissa & Willett, 2018). By addressing the challenges identified and fostering a culture of lifelong learning, librarians can continue to play a vital role in supporting teaching, learning, and research in the digital age.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the study's findings highlight the relationship between professional competence and job performance of librarians, underscoring their significant contributions to supporting teaching, learning, and research within the institution. While librarians demonstrate proficiency in various areas, including information retrieval, technology integration, and collaboration, notable challenges, such as budget constraints and inadequate training opportunities, hinder their effectiveness in fulfilling their roles, particularly in open and distance learning. However, the positive correlation between professional competence and job performance emphasizes investing in continuous professional development initiatives to empower librarians to overcome these challenges and thrive in the rapidly evolving digital landscape. By addressing these challenges and fostering a culture of lifelong learning and innovation, librarians can continue to play a pivotal role in advancing the institution's mission and goals, ultimately enhancing the quality of services provided to users and contributing to the overall success and reputation of the library.

Recommendation

Based on the findings and conclusions drawn from the study, here are three recommendations to address the challenges and further enhance the effectiveness of librarians within the open and distance learning context at the National Open University of Nigeria:

1. The institution should prioritize allocating resources to comprehensive professional development programs tailored to librarians' unique needs in the digital academic environment.
2. The institution should foster stronger collaborations between librarians and faculty members to integrate library resources seamlessly into distance learning courses.
3. Librarians should ensure that digital resources and services provided by the library are accessible to all users, including those with disabilities.

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